

Inference of light-source positions and of transparency in brightness illusion displays

Seiyu Sohmiya

e-mail: QZM01576@nifty.ne.jp

Abstract. Although many researchers have attempted to explain brightness illusions, no consensus agreement has yet been reached. I here report that two factors are essential to the study of brightness illusions, and propose a Helmholtzian explanation for the illusions based on differences of logical interpretations for the displays. The factors that there are: (1) a possibility that our visual system unconsciously infers three light-source positions for segments in the displays (the front of the segments, the segments themselves, and the area behind the segments) and (2) a possibility that our visual system interprets a non-transparent achromatic segment not only as a non-transparent surface illuminated from the side, but also as a transparent segment illuminated from behind, a shade, a cast shadow, a self-luminous segment, or a space. If our visual system take the factors into account and selects the more likely interpretations out of possible interpretations, it is unsurprising that segments that are physically identical gray is perceived as a different brightness in each situation.

1 Introduction

The question of how the visual system solves the problem of brightness perception is still open. Figure 1a shows an example of simultaneous brightness contrast. In this flat display, a gray circle surrounded completely by a black background is perceived as being brighter than a gray circle surrounded completely by a white background though the two circles are physically identical.

Figure 1. (a) An example of simultaneous brightness contrast. A gray circle on a black background appears brighter than a physically identical gray circle on a white background. (b) An example of White's effect (White 1979). A gray rectangle on a white background appears brighter than a physically identical gray rectangle on a black background. White's effect illusion is larger than simultaneous brightness contrast illusion.

However, as shown in figure 1b, it is also well known that when a gray rectangle is embedded in a white bar, the rectangle in a white bar is not perceived as being brighter than an identical rectangle embedded in a black bar. Even though a larger percentage of the area around the gray rectangle on the white bar is black compared to the gray rectangle on a black bar, the rectangle in the white bar is perceived as being darker than the rectangle in the black bar. Moreover, the brightness of the second illusion of the display in Figure 1b appears greater than that of the first simultaneous brightness contrast display in

Figure 1a. This illusion is called White's effect (White 1979). How can we explain this asymmetry?

Many researchers have discussed theoretical explanations for both simultaneous brightness contrast and White's effect based on low-level and/or mid-level mechanisms of our visual system (eg Todorovic 1997; Blakeslee and McCourt 1999; Gilchrist et al 1999; Kelly and Grossberg 2000; Ross and Pessoa 2000; Howe, 2001; Anderson 2003; Blakeslee et al 2005). However, there is still no consensus as to why we perceive physically identical achromatic segments in illusion displays as differing in brightness.

Here, I propose that two factors that have received little discussion in previous works (e.g., Wallach 1948; Gilchrist 1979; White 1979; Knill and Kersten 1991; Adelson 1993; Anderson 1997; Kingdom 1997; Schirillo and Shevell 1997; Zaidi et al 1997; Blakeslee and McCourt 1999; Gilchrist et al 1999; Bonato and Cataliotti 2000; Kelly and Grossberg 2000; Ross and Pessoa 2000; Howe, 2001; Anderson 2003; McCourt and Foxe 2004; Purves et al 2004; Blakeslee et al 2005) are essential to the study of perceived brightness. I also propose a Helmholtzian explanation of the illusions based on differences in logical interpretations of the flat displays (eg Gregory 1970, 1972; Rock and Anson 1979; Anderson 1997; Sohmiya 2004).

The two factors that I suggest are as follows:

(1) the possibility that our visual system infers that there are three interpretations of light-source positions within the displays (that is, the front of the segments (Ramachandran 1988; Sun and Perona 1998), the segments themselves (Bonato and Cataliotti 2000), and the area behind the segments); and (2) the possibility that our visual system interprets a non-transparent achromatic segment not only as a non-transparent achromatic surface, but also as a transparent surface illuminated from behind the segments, a shade, a cast shadow, a self-luminous segment (Land and McCann 1971; Blakeslee and McCourt 1999; Bonato and Cataliotti 2000; Blakeslee et al 2005), or a space.

If our visual system unconsciously takes these two factors into account to solve a problem of what a gray segment in a brightness illusion display is, and then selects a plausible interpretation at any given moment from multiple possibilities, with the selected interpretation either remaining stable or alternating over time depending on the stimulus. (e.g., Gregory 1970, 1972; Rock and Anson 1979; Anderson 1997; Sohmiya 2004), it is not surprising that physically identical gray segments can be perceived as differing in brightness in

each situation.

2 Experiment 1: Inference of three light-source positions in pictures

Experiment 1 was performed to examine the inferences for the light-source positions in pictures and the “object-reality” (Gregory 1970) of each display by our visual system.

Figure 2. Inference of light-source positions in achromatic pictures and interpretations of them. (a) Sunset. (b) Mountain and cloud. (c) A climber on a rock. (d) The moon. Reported light-source positions were as follows: a; The white circle itself (a1), b; The area behind section b1, c; The front of the climber (c1), and d; White circle itself (d1). Moreover, the “object-reality”(Gregory 1970) of each light-source was as follows: a-c; The sun, d; The moon.

2.1 Method

2.1.1 *Observers.* Ten subjects participated in the observations. All the subjects had normal or corrected-to-normal acuity. They were naive as to the purpose of the experiment.

2.1.2 *Stimuli.* Figure 2 a-d were printed with black ink on a white copy paper

with a Hewlett Packard 880c inkjet printer. The four pictures measured 10cm square in height and width. The viewing distance was about 57cm with 10 mm on the stimulus field subtending 1° degree of visual angle.

2.1.3 *Procedure.* The figures (figure 2a-d) were presented one time to the subjects in sunlight. The subjects were asked to guess the light-source positions in each picture and to explain the “object-reality” of each picture. They were not instructed what the pictures were. They observed the pictures with no limit on inspection time. The illumination was about 3500 lx.

2.2 *Results and Discussion*

When the displays (figure 2a-d) were presented to ten naive subjects in sunlight, they guessed the light-source positions as follows: for figure 2a it was at the white circle itself (a1); for figure 2b it was at the area behind the section b1; for figure 2c it was at the front of the climber (c1); and for figure 2d it was at the white circle itself (d1) though they knew that the configurations were presented in sunlight.

Moreover, my results show that our visual system guesses the “object-reality” of the light-source in each display. Because all the subjects reported that the light-sources in figure 2a-c were the sun and the light-source in figure 2d was the moon. In addition, they have understood that the moon is not a light-source, but rather is illuminated by the sun. However, they perceived it as if it was in self-luminous mode.

My results of the first experiment suggest that, when a real world scene is represented from information of achromatic pictures, our visual system infers three light-source positions in the pictures, that is, the front of segments, segments themselves, and/or the area behind segments.

3 Experiment 2: Inference of transparency in perspective display

The degree of transparency of objects is one of the most important information received by our visual system when we see objects in a real world (Anderson 1997). If a non-transparent object is illuminated, a shade and/or a cast shadow appears. On the other hand, if a transparent object is illuminated, a perceptual transparency occurs.

Here a question arises: how does our visual system interpret the degree of transparency of each non-transparent segment in achromatic pictures?

Experiment 2 was performed to examine the inferences for the light-source positions and of the degree of transparency of each non-transparent segment in an achromatic picture.

Figure 3. Inference of transparency in a perspective display (modified from Gilchrist 1979). All the subjects interpreted the gray patches of a, b, and c as a non-transparent surface illuminated from the side, as a cast shadow, and as a transparent surface illuminated from the area behind the patch c, respectively.

3.1 Method

3.1.1 *Observers.* The subjects were the same as in the first experiment.

3.1.2 *Stimuli.* Figure 3 (Gilchrist 1979) was printed with black ink on a white copy paper with a Hewlett Packard 880c inkjet printer. The display measured 9cm in height and 13cm in width. The viewing distance was about 57cm with 10 mm on the stimulus field subtending 1° degree of visual angle.

3.1.3 *Procedure.* Figure 3 was presented one time to the subjects in sunlight. The subjects were asked to guess the light-source positions in the perspective display and to explain three patches a, b, and c. They were not instructed what the display and the three patches were. They observed the display with no limit on inspection time. The illumination was about 3500 lx.

3.2 Results and Discussion

All the subjects reported that (1) the light-source position was the area behind the patch c and the light-source was the sun and (2) the patch a, b, and c were a surface illuminated from the side, a cast shadow, and a transparent surface illuminated from the area behind the patch c, respectively.

My results show that our visual system represents the degree of transparency of

the achromatic patches of the perspective display in each situation as though they are physically non-transparent. Are the inferences done for flat displays?

Consider the interpretations in a real world for the flat display illustrated in figure 4 (Bonato and Cataliotti 2000) supposing only one light-source position for efficiency. If the black section of the display is figure and the white section of the display is ground, the black figure has at least six interpretations as shown figure 5 (1)-(6). First, if the light-source position in the display is at the front of the black figure, three interpretations are possible: (1) a black face illustrated on a white paper; (2) a black face in front of a white surface; and (3) a cast shadow of a face on a white surface. Second, if the light-source position in the display is in the area behind the black figure, two interpretations are possible: (4) a cast shadow of a face on a transparent white surface; and (5) a self-shade of a face created by an intense light source coming from behind the face and the white section is a space. Finally, if the light-source position in the display is at the display itself, the only possible interpretation is (6) that only the white section is in self-luminous mode.

Where is the light-source in the display?
What object is this display?

Figure 4. A face-shaped flat display (modified from Bonato and Cataliotti 2000).

Experiment 3: The logical interpretations for a face-shaped flat display

The object of experiment 3 was to verify which interpretations mentioned above are selected by our visual system for figure 4.

4.1 Method

4.1.1 *Observers.* The subjects were the same as in the first experiment.

4.1.2 *Stimuli.* Figure 4 was printed with black ink on a white copy paper with a Hewlett Packard 880c inkjet printer. The display measured 8cm in height and 7cm in width. The viewing distance was about 57cm with 10 mm on the stimulus field subtending 1° degree of visual angle.

4.1.3 *Procedure.* Figure 4 was presented one time to the subjects in sunlight. The subjects were asked to guess the light-sources positions in figure 4 and to explain the “object-reality” of the black section in the display. They were not instructed what the display and three patches were. They observed the display with no limit on inspection time. The illumination was about 3500 lx.

4.2 Results and Discussion

One subject reported the interpretations (1) and (2) and inferred that the light-source position was only at the front of the face. Four subjects reported the interpretations (1) and (3) and inferred that the light-source position was only at the front of the face. The other five subjects reported interpretations (1), (3), and (4) and inferred that the light-source position was at the front of the face or in the area behind the face. No one reported the interpretations (5) and (6) (see Figure. 5) .

Thus, my results show that our visual system can select at least two possibilities of light-source positions in the flat display and that there are multiple interpretations for the black figure. In other words, the black figure in figure 4 is an ambiguous figure both in its "object reality" and its light-source position.

5 General Discussion

Although several models (Todorovic 1997; Blakeslee and McCourt 1999; Gilchrist et al 1999; Kelly and Grossberg 2000; Ross and Pessoa 2000; Howe, 2001; Anderson 2003; Blakeslee et al 2005) have been proposed to explain both simultaneous brightness contrast and White's effect, no definite agreement has been reached yet. However, I believe that, if one assumes that our visual system always infers three light-source positions in a display and, at the same time, interprets the degree of transparency of each segment in the display, and

Figure 5. The logical interpretations for a face-shaped flat display. This display has at least the six interpretations; (1)-(6). The reported results indicated that for this display our visual system inferred at least two light-source positions and interpreted the figure not only as a black face, but also as a cast shadow of a face, or a shade of a face.

then takes the two factors into account to solve a problem of what the display is (Rock and Anson 1979), both the two illusions can be explained within Gregory's theory (Gregory 1970, 1972) that “perception involves a kind of inference from sensory data to object-reality” (Gregory 1970).

Where is the light-source in the display? & What object is this?

Figure 6. A Helmholtzian explanation of simultaneous brightness contrast. a1-a6 and b1-b6 are the typical interpretations of the circles A and B, respectively. Each bracket shows the brightness judgment of each circle in each interpretation. For a1-a6, $[A] \geq \text{gray}$. While, for b1-b6, $\text{gray} \geq [B]$. Then, $[A] \geq [B]$. Here, if our visual system selects at least one interpretation out of a4-a6, then $[A] > [B]$. Thus, the circle A appears brighter than the circle B. $[A]$ and $[B]$ are the brightness judgments of the circles A and B, respectively.

Consider first simultaneous brightness contrast supposing only one light-source position for efficiency. As shown a1- a6 in figure 6, a gray circle A on a black square has at least the following six interpretations to be tested by our visual system: (a1) a gray circle on a black square illuminated from the side; (a2) a gray square behind a black square with a hole and the light-source is at the front of the black square; (a3) this is a gray square illuminated from the side and the black section is a shadow being cast on it; (a4) this is a black square illuminated from the side and circle A is strongly illuminated by the other light-source (a circle of light) from the side; (a5) a transparent gray circle illuminated from behind; and (a6) a gray circle in self-luminous mode. Then, the brightness judgments of the circle A by our visual system are gray for the interpretations a1, a2, and a3 and they are bright gray for the interpretations a4, a5, and a6. Thus, the brightness judgment of the circle A by our visual system is more than or equal to gray, that is, $[A] \geq \text{gray}$. Where $[A]$ is the brightness judgment of the circle A by our visual system.

On the other hand, as shown b1-b6 in figure 6, a gray circle B on a white square also has at least the following six interpretations to be tested by our visual system: (b1) a gray circle on a white square illuminated from the side; (b2) a gray square behind a white square with a hole and the light-source is at the front of the white square; (b3) this is a white square illuminated from the side and this gray circle is a shadow being cast on it; (b4) this is a gray square illuminated from the side and white section is strongly illuminated by the other light-source (a square-ring of light) from the side; (b5) a shade projected on a transparent white square illuminated from behind; and (b6) a gray circle and a white section in self-luminous mode. Then, the brightness judgments of the circle B by our visual system are gray for the interpretations b1, b2, b3, and b5 and they are gray or dark gray for the interpretations b4 and b6. Thus, the brightness judgment of the circle B by our visual system is less than or equal to gray, that is, $\text{gray} \geq [B]$. Where $[B]$ is the brightness judgment of the circle B by our visual system.

In sum, for the brightness judgments of the two circles by our visual system, we have $[A] \geq [B]$. Because $[A] \geq \text{gray}$ and $\text{gray} \geq [B]$. Here, if our visual system selects at least one interpretation of the circle A as bright gray, then $[A] > [B]$. Consequently, we perceive the circle A as being brighter than the circle B.

Consider next White's effect supposing only one light-source position for efficiency. As shown x1- x6 in figure 7, a gray rectangle X on a black bar has at

Figure 7. A Helmholtzian explanation of White's effect. x1-x6 and y1-y6 are the typical interpretations of the rectangles X and Y, respectively. Each bracket shows the brightness judgment of each rectangle in each interpretation. For x1-x6, $[X] \geq \text{gray}$. While $\text{gray} \geq [Y]$ for y1-y6. Hence, $[X] \geq [Y]$. Here, if our visual system selects at least one interpretation out of x4-x6, then $[X] > [Y]$. Thus, the rectangle X appears brighter than the rectangle Y.

least the following six interpretations to be tested by our visual system: (x1) a gray rectangle on a black bar illuminated from the side; (x2) a gray rectangle behind two black rectangles and they are illuminated from the side; (x3) this bar is a gray bar illuminated from the side and each black section is a cast shadow; (x4) this bar is a black bar illuminated from the side and only the gray rectangle is strongly illuminated by the other light-source from the side; (x5) a transparent gray rectangle illuminated from behind; and (x6) a gray rectangle in self-luminous mode. Then, the brightness judgments of the rectangle X by our visual system are gray for the interpretation x1, x2, and x3, and they are bright gray for the interpretations x4, x5, and x6. Thus, the brightness judgment of the rectangle X by our visual system is more than or equal to gray, that is, $[X] \geq \text{gray}$. Where $[X]$ is the brightness judgment of the rectangle X by our visual system.

On the other hand, as shown y1-y6 in figure 7, a gray rectangle Y on a white bar also has at least the following six interpretations to be tested by our visual system: (y1) a gray rectangle on a white bar illuminated from the side; (y2) a gray rectangle behind two white rectangles and they are illuminated from the side; (y3) a cast shadow on a white bar illuminated from the side; (y4) this bar is a gray bar illuminated from the side and each white section is strongly illuminated by the other light-source from the side; (y5) a shade projected on a transparent white surface illuminated from behind; and (y6) a gray rectangle and a white section in self-luminous mode. Then, the brightness judgments of the rectangle Y by our visual system are gray for the interpretations y1, y2, y3, and y5 and they are gray or dark gray for the interpretations y4 and y6. Thus, the brightness judgment of the rectangle Y by our visual system is less than or equal to gray, that is, $\text{gray} \geq [Y]$. Where $[Y]$ is the brightness judgment of the rectangle Y by our visual system.

In sum, for the brightness judgments of the two rectangles by our visual system, we have $[X] \geq [Y]$. Because $[X] \geq \text{gray}$ and $\text{gray} \geq [Y]$. Here, if our visual system selects at least one interpretation of rectangle X as bright gray, then $[X] > [Y]$. Consequently, we perceive the rectangle X as being brighter than the rectangle Y.

Finally, consider the well-known observation that “illusion magnitude” (Anderson 1997) of White's effect display is larger than that of simultaneous contrast display. For the White's effect display in figure 7, if our visual system selects only the interpretation x4 as the interpretation of the rectangle X and

selects only the interpretation y_3 as the interpretation of the rectangle Y. In this case, the rectangle X is interpreted only as light and the rectangle Y is interpreted only as a cast shadow. Moreover, for the brightness judgment of each rectangle by our visual system, $[X] = \text{bright gray}$ and $[Y] = \text{gray}$. Hence, $[X] > [Y]$. While, for the simultaneous brightness contrast display in figure 6, if our visual system selects the interpretations a_1 and a_5 as the interpretations of the circle A and selects the interpretations b_1 and b_5 as the interpretations of the circle B. In this case, for the brightness judgment of each circle by our visual system, $[A]$ is between gray and bright gray and $[B]$ is gray, that is, $\text{bright gray} > [A] > \text{gray}$ and $[B] = \text{gray}$. Hence, $[A] > [B]$. In sum, for the brightness judgments of the four target segments by our visual system, $[X] > [A] > [B] = [Y]$. Thus, the difference between $[X]$ and $[Y]$ is larger than the difference between $[A]$ and $[B]$. Consequently, if our visual system selects the above six interpretations, then White's effect should be larger than simultaneous brightness contrast illusion.

Although I consider that my explanations based on the differences of preferred interpretations for the target segments are effective for the two illusions, several questions still remain: (1) which interpretations are selected as more preferred ones; (2) which interpretations are rejected as unlikely ones; and (3) what perceptual rules apply to the decisions?

For example, for the simultaneous brightness contrast in figure 6, if only the interpretation a_1 is selected as the interpretation of the circle A and only the interpretation b_1 is selected as the interpretation of the circle B, since the brightness judgments for the two circles are identical, we should perceive the two circles as equal brightness. However, we perceive the circle A as being brighter than the circle B. Then, I assumed that our visual system selects at least one interpretation that $[A]$ is bright gray. Moreover, if our visual system judges that $[B]$ is bright gray for the interpretation b_5 and selects only this interpretation, we should perceive the circle B approximately as bright as the circle A. However, we perceive the circle B as being darker than the circle A. Hence, I assumed that our visual system rejects the interpretation or does not select it. Although the above assumptions are supported by previous theories (Blakeslee and McCourt 1999; Gilchrist 1999; Ross and Pessoa 2000; Blakeslee et al 2005), they have further aspects to be discussed.

In conclusion, by assuming that our visual system infers the light-source positions in flat displays and interprets an achromatic non-transparent segment

in the displays not only as a non-transparent surface but also as a transparent surface illuminated from behind, a shade, a cast shadow, a self-luminous segment, or a space, both simultaneous brightness contrast and White's effect can be explained based on the difference of "object-reality" for each target segment. If this Helmholtzian explanation is correct, not only low-level and/or mid-level mechanisms, but also high-level mechanisms play an important role in the illusions (Adelson 1997). I believe that the illusions are good examples that the Helmholtzian views (Gregory 1970, 1972; Rock and Anson 1979; Adelson 1993; Anderson 1997; Sun and Perona 1998; Sohmiya 2004) are essential to study the problems of perception.

Acknowledgments. I thank Tamotsu Sohmiya and Kazuko Sohmiya for their comments on the manuscript and Tomoyuki Uchida for permission of reprint of figure 2a, b, and d.

References

- Adelson E H, 1993 "Perceptual organization and the judgment of brightness" *Science* **262** 2042-2044
- Anderson B L, 1997 "A theory of illusory lightness and transparency in monocular and binocular images: the role of contour junctions" *Perception* **26** 419-453
- Anderson B L, 2003 "Perceptual organization and White's illusion" *Perception* **32** 269-284
- Blakeslee B, McCourt M E, 1999 "A multiscale spatial filtering account of the White effect, simultaneous brightness contrast and grating induction" *Vision Research* **39** 4361-4377
- Blakeslee B et al, 2005 "Oriented multiscale spatial filtering and contrast normalization: a parsimonious model of brightness induction in a continuum of stimuli including White, Howe and simultaneous brightness contrast" *Vision Research* **45** 607-615
- Bonato F, Cataliotti J, 2000 "The effects of figure/ground, perceived area, and target saliency on the luminosity threshold" *Perception & Psychophysics* **62** 341-349
- Gilchrist A, 1979 "The perception of surface blacks and whites" *Scientific American* **240** 88-97
- Gilchrist A et al, 1999 "An anchoring theory of lightness perception" *Psychological Review* **106** 795-834
- Gregory R L, 1970 *The Intelligent Eye* (Weldenfeld and Nicolson, London)
- Gregory R L, 1972 "Cognitive Contours" *Nature* **238** 51-52
- Howe P D L, 2001 "A comment on the Anderson (1997), the Todorovic (1997),

- and the Ross and Pessoa (2000) explanations of White's effect" *Perception* **30** 1023-1026
- Kelly F, Grossberg S, 2000 "Neural dynamics of 3-D surface perception: Figure-ground separation and lightness perception" *Perception & Psychophysics* **62** 1596-1618
- Kingdom F, 1997 "Simultaneous contrast: the legacies of Hering and Helmholtz" *Perception* **26** 673-677.
- Knill D C, Kersten D, 1991 "Apparent surface curvature affects lightness perception" *Nature* **351** 228-230
- Land E H, McCann J J, 1971 "Lightness and retinex theory" *Journal of the Optical Society of America* **61** 1-11
- McCourt M E, Foxe J J, 2004 "Brightening prospects for early cortical coding of perceived luminance: a high-density electrical mapping study" *NeuroReport* **15** 49-56
- Purves D et al, 2004 "Perceiving the intensity of light" *Psychological Review* **111** 142-158
- Ramachandran V S, 1988 "Perception of shape from shading" *Nature* **331** 163-166
- Rock I, Anson R, 1979 "Illusory contours as the solution to a problem" *Perception* **8** 665-681
- Ross W D, Pessoa L, 2000 "Lightness from contrast: A selective integration model" *Perception & Psychophysics* **62** 1160-1181
- Schirillo J A, Shevell S K, 1997 "An account of brightness in complex scenes based on inferred illumination" *Perception* **26** 507-518
- Sohmiya S, 2004 "Explanation for neon color effect of chromatic configurations on the basis of perceptual ambiguity in form and color" *Perceptual Motor Skills* **98** 272-290
- Sun J, Perona P, 1998 "Where is the sun?" *Nature neuroscience* **1** 183-184
- Todorovic D, 1997 "Lightness and junctions" *Perception* **26** 379-394
- Wallach H, 1948 "Brightness constancy and the nature of achromatic colors" *Journal of Experimental Psychology* **38** 310-324
- White M, 1979 "A new effect of pattern on perceived lightness" *Perception* **8** 413-416
- Zaidi Q et al, 1997 "Induced effects of backgrounds and foregrounds in three-dimensional configurations: the role of T-junctions" *Perception* **26** 395-408